

B.Tec. Degree in Construction Technology and Resource Management

Work-Based Final Report

**Evaluation on Pre-Construction Stage of Rural Roads Constructed
Under "Sapirigamak" Rural Development Programme - 2020,
Kalutara District, Sri Lanka.**

By

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Declaration

“ I certify that this report does not incorporate without acknowledgement any materials previously submitted for an any other module and to the best of my knowledge and belief that it does not contain any material previously published or written or orally communicated by another person except where due reference is made in the text”.

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To the best of my / our knowledge the above particulars are correct.

Signature (s)
Name (s) of the supervisor (s).....
Designation of the supervisor (s).....

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List of Abbreviations

RDP – Rural Development programme
GDP – Gross Domestic Product
GN – Grama Niladhari
Admin. – Administration
Approx. - Approximately
ILB – Interlocking block
Avg. – Average
GN – Grama Niladhari
DO – Development Officer
SDO – Samurdhi development Office
ARPA – Agricultural research and production assistant

CHAPTER 1

1.1 Introduction

Over the years Sri Lankan government is increasingly focusing on rural road construction because there are economic and social benefits which enable transportation of people, material and goods and improve agriculture, Industry and services.

Rural road construction in Sri Lanka is mainly undertaken by local authorities such as Urban Councils, Municipal Councils and Divisional Secretariat offices. Every government has a rural development program in their development plans. In 2018 “Gampaeraliya” rural development program, in 2020 “Sapiri Gamak” rural development program and planning to launch “Gama Samaga Pilisadarak” rural development program in this year 2022 in order to enrich rural areas.

Kalutara district is the second level administrative district among 25 districts of Sri Lanka. Which is divided into 14 divisional secretariats and further divided into 762 Grama Niladhari Divisions. Kalutara district is a mix of urban and rural areas. (Anon., n.d.)

Kalutara district is a district in western province which is the forerunner in Sri Lankan economy with the highest Gross Domestic product (GDP) share of 39.1%. There are a lot of economic activities in Kalutara district. There is a BOI zone in Horana, and there are a lot of industries. As a coastal area there is tourism industry. Contributing fairly in agricultural activities services in terms of GDP. (Lanka, 2020)

In Kalutara district there are 02 interchanging points to southern expressway and around 03 interchanging points to proposed Ruwanpura expressway and there is a good arterial road network. Also, there is coastal railway line.

Figure 1-1 – Road network in Kalutara District

In Sri Lanka there are several rural road construction methods, i.e.

- i. Cast in situ concrete road construction
- ii. Macadam road construction
- iii. Interlocking paving block construction
- iv. Earth Road

1.2 Background

“Sapirigamak” is the nearest past rural development program which was implemented covering the entire country. Under the “Sapirigamak” program each Grama niladari division got approx. LKR 2,000,000/- for the rural development projects. Total project value is 28 Billion and total project value for kalutara district is 1.5 Billion. (portal, 2020) According to the sources of District secretariat kalutara, under “Sapirigamak” RDP around 88% of the implemented projects were rural road development projects and there was some building construction, Irrigation and water supply projects.

There are no direct financial benefits for the economy from rural road development. Construction of rural roads can facilitate and boost economic development activities such as agriculture, industries, services, etc. and influencing indirectly on the economy of the country. So, it is very important to develop rural roads in order to enhance economic and social development of Sri Lanka.

1.3 Problem Statement

According to the preference of the Provincial Politicians, roads were chosen under “Gamperaliya” rapid rural development program in 2018. However, in the “Sapiri Gamak” rural development program in 2020, roads were picked out according to the decisions made via a committee consists of Development Officers, Grama Niladhari officers, samurdhi officers, and provincial political representatives.

Other than from massive rural development programs annually there are road construction projects from the decentralized budget program. Yet, due to the insufficient technical guidance on proper feasibility studies and significant amount of political interference, still there were flaws can be seen during the constructions mentioned above.

Though the government spend lots of money on rural road development programs, there is a problem that the current economic situation and declination of economic indices make a doubt that does the expenditure on rural road development actually boost the economy of Sri Lanka.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a development indicator of a country. According to figure 02 graph annual GDP growth rate of Sri Lanka is decreasing drastically.

Rural road construction in Sri Lanka is a most criticized area currently with the economic crisis in Sri Lanka. So, it is very important to do a proper study on previous projects and improve rural road development in Sri Lanka.

Figure 1-2 - Annual GDP Growth rate in Sri Lanka (Lanka, 2020)

There are mainly three stages can be seen in the rural road construction. They are pre construction stage, construction stage and the post construction stage. When considering these phases pre construction stage is the most important because in rural road construction this is the most corrupted. A sustainable development can be achieved through further improvement in pre-construction phase.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

1.4.1 Aim

- To evaluate the pre-construction stage of rural roads constructed under "sapirigamak" rural development programme – 2020 in Kalutara district.

1.4.2 Objectives

- To study the pre-construction stage of the rural road development of "Sapirigamak" RDP in Kalutara district.
- To analyze and identify projects that can effectively contribute to the socio-economic development and to identify non-effective projects by a follow up survey.
- To propose recommendations for a pre project stage of a rural road that can contributes to socio-economic development

CHAPTER 2

2.1 Literature Review

As the increase in constructions of many things including roads, buildings and bridges etc. in the world, researches done on the same subject has been increased due to the problems faced in the so-called sector.

According to (Anon., 2020) Rural roads are, an important enabling condition for livelihood development for people in the project sites and the study confirms that better rural roads are a necessary but not sufficient condition for graduating from poverty. as found in the study on “Impact of rural roads on poverty reduction” done by Asian Development Bank. This finding can be verified through the current proposal, as it is done by a sample selected from one of the rural developing villages in the country.

According to (Asher & Novosad, 2019) Many of the world’s poorest live in places that are not well connected to outside markets. The resulting high transportation costs potentially inhibit gains from the division of labor, specialization, and economies of scale. New paved roads lead to increased transportation services and a large reallocation of labor out of agriculture. This paper suggests that even in a fast-growing economy such as India in the 2000s, rural growth is constrained by more than the poor state of transportation infrastructure. Instead of facilitating growth on village farms and firms, the main economic benefit of rural transportation infrastructure may be the connection of rural workers to new employment opportunities.

According to (Parry, 1985) From the evidence available, concrete should be considered as an alternative form of construction, particularly in those - developing countries with indigenous cement manufacturing capability. This finding stimulates the idea of constructing concrete roads in rural villages are more advantageous than other roads.

According to (Fuchs & Sion, n.d.) Most rural roads in Belgium are constructed in cement concrete. The use of high-production laying techniques has led to construction costs that are lower than those of equivalent flexible structures. The performance of rural roads in concrete has also proved to be excellent in the long term, because they require virtually no maintenance. These construction techniques are also suitable for developing countries that have plentiful cement supplies. Rural roads in concrete can be constructed by local contractors using either very simple labor-intensive equipment or special equipment, depending on the circumstances.

According to (Vohra & Sharma, 2009) The present pace of road infrastructure development is inadequate in India vis-à-vis other developing economies. The quality of roads compared with China is far below expectations and this poor hinterland connectivity is affecting the trade growth in the country.

According to (Liming Chen, 2021) a study on Integrated Road Investment Program (iRoad) in Sri Lanka, improving rural connectivity can ease development constraints, increase resilience in managing negative economic shocks caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, and contribute to post-pandemic economic recovery. The findings also lend to the idea that targeted placements based on the beneficiary's location, socioeconomic centers and complementary infrastructure (e.g., educational and medical facilities) can enhance the effectiveness of rural road investments.

According to (A.ArunaShantha, 2019) report on The IROAD project in Sri Lanka it concludes that road development influence to change social and economic activities people who are living in the project area. Among these changes, the most positive impacts are made on household income, land value, travel time saving, private vehicle usage, employment opportunities and connectivity of socio-economic centers.

When referring literature there are research studies which was done on construction stage and post construction stage on rural road construction, but there is a gap of research in the area of pre-construction stage of rural road construction, so it is vital to do a research on pre-construction stage of rural road construction.

More the researches done on construction field; more it's determined that it enhances the values of building roads in order to improve the quality of living of the users of the constructed roads.

CHAPTER 3

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Introduction

This is a survey type descriptive research and research approach is a blend of qualitative and quantitative. In this chapter the methodology employed to carry out the research is described.

Figure 3-1 – Flow chart of Methodology

3.1.2 Population

Population includes all the rural roads constructed under “Sapirigamak” RDP in Kalutara district Sri Lanka in 2020. As per the secondary data collected from District Secretariat Kalutara 2487 projects were completed under “Sapirigamak” RDP in Kalutara district. Out of all the projects 2192 (Around 88% from total projects) were rural road development projects which is the population in this research study. Other projects were building construction and renovation, Irrigation and water supply projects.

3.1.3 Sampling

A sample is only a portion of the population. To find the minimum sample size for the study Yamane's formula was applied.

Yamane's formula,

$$n = N / (1+N(e^2))$$

n - sample size

N - Population size

e – Level of precision

Considering confidence level as – 85%

$$e = \pm 15\%$$

$$N = 2192$$

$$\text{Sample size} = N / (1+N(e^2)) = 2192 / (1+2192(0.15^2)) = \underline{43.5}$$

Multistage Sampling technique was employed to select the sample. Under the “Sapirigamak” RDP in Kalutara district rural roads were constructed by 02 authorities,

- Divisional Secretariats – 1506 projects were implemented
- Municipal Councils / Urban Councils - 686 projects were implemented

Rural roads implemented under *Divisional Secretariats* were selected by following convenience sampling technique. Because Majority of the rural road projects were implemented by the Divisional secretariats and there are field officers in every GN division and there is a strong secondary data base which can be really effective in accurate data collection.

Further simple random sampling was employed and selected 56 rural roads *Annexure 01* (To represent 14 Divisional Secretariats in Kalutara district randomly selected 04 Nos. of roads from each divisional secretariat.) out of 1506 projects which was the sample selected by convenience sampling method.

3.1.4 Data Collection

The structure of questionnaire was developed in order to study the pre-construction stage of the rural road development of “Sapirigamak” RDP in Kalutara district. The questionnaire format was easy to understand and answer the target respondents and it used to collect more accurate and necessary information related to the pre-construction stage of “Sapirigamak” RDP in Kalutara district from professionals who engaged in project works. The questionnaire *Annexure 02* was categorized as follows.

- Personal Details
- Overall Impression on the” sapirigamak" RDP
- Pre-Construction Stage - Feasibility Study
- Pre-Construction Stage - Fund Allocation/Estimation/Contract

Likert scale was employed to measure multidimensional attitudes. Pilot questionnaire survey was conducted with professionals and experts and corrected minor errors.

To analyze and identify projects that can effectively contribute to the socio-economic development and to identify non-effective projects by a follow up survey is another objective of the study. In the follow up survey study some important secondary data were collected from project estimates, contract documents, reports etc.

And primary data was collected from site investigation, interviews with the field officers in charge of sample roads, interviews with the civilians who are using sample roads and final output was taken into a sample survey report (*Annexure 03*).

Data was collected to assess Connectivity to socio-economic centers, accessibility, mobility etc. Pilot follow-up survey study was conducted and corrected minor errors.

And also, primary data are collected from unstructured interview from selected panel of experts to apply to the identification process of socioeconomically advantageous and disadvantageous projects. And expert reviews are expected to use to propose recommendations for a pre project stage of a rural road that can contributes to socio-economic development.

3.1.5 Analysis

Collected data from questionnaire and follow up survey are analyzed by descriptive analysis and graphical method. Collected primary data from the questionnaires are analyzed to study how the pre-construction phase processes (feasibility study, Estimation, fund allocation and contract admin.) were conducted under "sapirigamak" rural development programme – 2020 in Kalutara district. Collected secondary and primary data from the follow-up survey study are analyzed to identify projects that can effectively contribute to the socio-economic development and to identify non-effective projects in terms of socio-economic development.

And also collected primary data from unstructured interview from selected panel of experts are analyzed through descriptive analysis method to apply to the identification process of socioeconomically advantageous and disadvantageous projects.

CHAPTER 4

4.1 Analysis

The most crucial portion of a research is the analysis of the particular thesis. It will conclude all the data collected by the author and the value of the research will be based on the quality of the analysis. Hence, this chapter will deliver an expressive investigation on the so-called sector which was discussed on previous chapters.

4.1.1 Questionnaire Analysis

Figure 4-1- "Sapiri gamak" RDP 2020, Compared to previous RDP.

According to the graph, majority of professionals think that the "Sapiri gamak" RDP 2020 is similar to previous RDP such as Gamperaliya 2018

Figure 4-2 - contribute to the economic development

Figure 4-3 - contribute to the social development

According to figure 4.2 & 3, majority of professionals think that the "Sapiri gamak" RDP 2020 not well planned to contribute to the economic and social development.

Figure 4-3 - proper feasibility study for the selection of rural roads among plenty of rural roads

According to above graph, all the professionals emphasized that there was no proper feasibility study done for the selection of rural roads among plenty of rural roads.

Figure 4-4 - Influence level for the selection of roads under "sapirigamak" Rural development Programme.

This concludes that, majority of the professionals emphasize that political influence is affected to road construction, where technical qualified professionals influence is almost nil. Also, other professionals influence was low.

Figure 4-5 - preferred road selection influence level of professionals

This concludes that, majority of the professionals prefer a high influence from technical qualified professionals in the road selection phase. And also, civilians influence is highly preferred by majority of the professionals. And majority of the professional’s states that political influence should be low.

Figure 4-6 – Consideration on development aspects when selecting a rural road

55.9% professionals think that priority should be given to projects which could contribute towards economic development and 41.2 %professionals think that both economic and social development should be consider when prioritization of roads.

Figure 4-7 – Prioritization of essential roads

61.8% of the professionals' state that when selecting rural roads essential roads were not given priority

Figure 4-8 – Fund allocation and Estimation

In the preliminary study stage, it was found that in RDP technical estimation was done after the fund allocation. Nearly 25% of professionals strongly disagree with that strategy While 55% Disagree. And also, majority of the professional disagree with the allocation of fix amount of money without considering completeness of the project and focusing of number of projects rather than completed projects.

Even though professionals feel that a fair amount of money allocated for the projects they strongly emphasize that politicians had the potential to significantly impact on money allocation and 80% of the professionals emphasize that it was apolitical trick to appease the people carrying out large number of projects with small project value.

Figure 4-9 – decision making on selection of road type

Professionals clearly emphasized that type of road selection decision was dominant by professionals and majority of professionals’ state that political and civilians had a moderate decision-making influence on the road type.

Figure 4-10 – Order of choice

Figure 4-11 – Factors considering for selecting of road type

According to above graphs majority of the professionals concerned about the cost when selecting the road type, and also concerned about other factors specially durability, environmental friendliness, and proper drainage. Majority of the professionals prefer earth roads as their first choice perhaps because of the cost and the environmental friendliness factor and more than 95 percent of the professionals prefer ILB roads as their first and second choice. More than 60 percent of the professionals preferred concrete roads as their first and second choice. None of the professionals preferred macadam roads as the first and second choice.

4.1.2 Follow up study

4.1.2.1 Construction method

Construction Method	No. of roads	Total Expenditure (Rs.)	Total area of construction (m ²)	Avg. Cost per m ² (Rs.)	Cost &coverage relative to concrete road
Concrete	46	23,975,000.00	8,206.99	2,921.29	1
ILB	4	2,000,000.00	444.63	4,498.12	0.65
Macadam	5	2,800,000.00	1,461.75	1915.51	1.52
Earth	1	500,000.00	341.70	1463.27	2

Table 4-1 – Field survey construction methods summary

Annexure 04 - Sample road type, cost and coverage area

According to the Field survey construction methods summary 82% of the rural roads were concrete roads ILB and macadam roads are around 08-09 % and earth roads are only 1.8% from total sample roads.

ILB roads cover less ground area compared to concrete roads but macadam roads and earth roads cover more ground area in comparison with concrete roads.

Though majority of the roads were constructed in concrete construction professionals prefer ILB and earth roads ahead of concrete roads. According to the expert review, after reviewing experts' impressions on questionnaire and field survey summery. ILB roads have good drainage properties where concrete is an impervious surface. And also, durable, in addition to the base additional quarry dust or sand layer is there in the ILB roads and the compressive strength of a paving block is about 25N/mm², where concrete construction was done with 20N/mm² concrete mix. Aesthetic appearance is better. As a limited budget is approving for each rural road, earth roads and macadam roads are a good option. But with the moderate influence of politicians in road type selection sometimes professionals have to select the road type satisfying the users as well as the politician of the respective village. Sometimes though the ILB is advantageous in terms of durability and strength is is better to execute the project in concrete or macadam considering the completeness of the project.

Macadam roads are less in strength and durability compared to concrete roads and it is not suitable for areas which have inundation problems and drainage issues which can be subject to fast deterioration.

4.1.2.2 Mobility of rural roads

Mobility is defined as the potential for movement specially in this scenario it refers to the difficulty level of road. Compared to collector roads and local roads mobility of rural roads are less. Difficulty level of a road should be a concern when doing a proper feasibility study for a rural road. If it is a very difficult road for transportation that road should be considered with special attention when picking roads for construction.

In the post feasibility study of rural roads constructed under sapirigamak rural development programme the difficulty level of the road was measured with user reviews. Randomly distributed a questionnaire to rate the difficulty level of road. And their answers were quantified through a Likert scale *Annexure 06*. All the roads improved the mobility after construction according to the user reviews.

Likert scale

1	→	Very Good
2	→	Good
3	→	Not Bad
4	→	Bad
5	→	Very Bad

4.1.2.3 Post feasibility study

Professionals emphasized that there was no proper feasibility study. And selection of roads was highly influenced by politicians. So, through the collected data from the field survey is analyzed and do a post feasibility analysis to identify projects that can effectively contribute to the socio-economic development and to identify non-effective projects.

Normalized factors and indices were defined by expert review and represent the feasibility of the project through a final score. And boundaries are defined by expert judgement.

In the post feasibility study, all the dimensions are available and it is necessary to generalize the equation.

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \frac{\text{User Housing units}}{\text{Coverage area(m}^2\text{)}} * \text{Length of road(m)}$$

Generalization,

Descriptive statics data,

<i>Coverage Area</i>		<i>Length of road(m)</i>	
Mean	186.6977	Mean	65.46
Median	170.1	Median	61.25
Mode	170.1	Mode	70.00
Range	309.55	Range	103.00
Minimum	102.9	Minimum	37.00
Maximum	412.45	Maximum	140.00
Sum	10455.07	Sum	3665.50
Count	56	Count	56.00

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} * \frac{\text{Length of road(m)}}{\text{Coverage area(m}^2\text{)}}$$

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} * \frac{65.46\text{m}}{196.7\text{m}^2}$$

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} / 3$$

As per the expert judgement low difficulty level (good mobility) rural road should be develop if the user housing units equals or more than 30 to gain socio economic benefits as the minimum requirement.

$$\text{Boundary score for feasibility check} = 30/3 = 10$$

So feasible project score ≥ 10

Difficulty factor factor (H)

Difficulty level

High – 1.5

Moderate – 1.25

Low -1

Difficulty level varies from 1-1.5 according to the difficulty level observed in the feasibility checking stage reasonable value can be use.

Economic/Social Development exceptions

Following exceptional socio-economic aspects were rated and imposed a score by expert judgment.

Class	Exceptions	Score
<u>Economic Exceptions</u>		
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export agricultural land • Consumption agricultural land • Factories • industries 	10
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A tourist attraction • Tourist hotel 	7
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-employed industries • Horticulture 	5
<u>Social Exceptions</u>		
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools 	7
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post office/Police station/Samurdhi bank • GN/DO/SDO/ARPA office • Clinics 	5
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious places/cemetery • play grounds and parks 	3

Table 4-2 - Economic/Social Development exceptions

Final feasibility check for rural roads

Generalized formula

Final score = (Utilization factor *Difficulty factor) + Socio Economic exception

Annexure 05 – Expert judgement

Annexure 07 – Post feasibility analysis

Figure 4-12 – Post feasibility study summary

According to the feasibility study only 27% of the projects are identified as feasible projects and 73% of the projects identified as non-feasible projects.

4.1.2.4 Completeness of projects

Professionals emphasized that it was a bad practice of allocating fix amount of money without considering completeness of the project and focusing of number of projects rather than completed projects.

Following result of follow up study *Annexure 08* suggest that majority of the projects are incomplete and there are reasonable number of projects where deficiency amount is equals or less than fifty thousand rupees.

Figure 4-13 – Completion of project

29% of the rural roads were completed while 71% of rural roads were in complete.

Figure 4-14 – Fund deficiency

Out of incomplete projects 25% of the projects fund deficiency to complete the project was equal or less than fifty thousand rupees.

CHAPTER 5

5.1 Conclusion

Road network and transportation facility development is important for socio economic development of the country. Therefore, effective rural road development can contribute significantly towards more socio-economic benefits.

The ultimate findings of the study contribute a lot for the improvement of rural road development in Sri Lanka. This research was aimed to evaluate the pre-construction stage of rural roads constructed under "sapirigamak" rural development programme – 2020 in Kalutara district which was a major project island wide expending 28 Billion on rural infrastructure development. Majority of the projects were rural road projects. This research was performed in kalutara district selecting 56 number of sample roads; however, this finding can be valid for all the rural road projects under the programme.

In the questionnaire survey which was performed with professionals who engaged in “Spairigamak” RDP 2020 to obtain attitudes about the rural road development and to study the RDP, data was collected and analyzed. Professionals emphasized that “Spairigamak” RDP 2020 was similar to other RDP executed in Sri Lanka.so the ultimate findings can be also applicable to RDP executed in Sri Lanka in recent past.

Professionals emphasized that there was no proper feasibility study so RDP 2020 was not well planned to contribute to the economic and social development. And selection of roads was highly influenced by politicians where technical qualified professionals influence was almost nil. In order to evaluate feasibility of the rural road projects constructed under the RDP relevant data was gathered from a field survey and analyzed to do a post feasibility analysis to identify projects that can effectively contribute to the socio-economic development and to identify non-effective projects.

Normalized factors and indices were defined by expert review and represent the feasibility of the project through a final score. And boundaries are defined by expert judgement.

According to the feasibility study only 27% of the projects are identified as feasible projects and 73% of the projects identified as non-feasible projects. And a generalized formula is formed to determine the feasibility of a rural road with expert judgement.

Generalized formula

Final score = (Utilization factor *Difficulty factor) + Socio Economic exception

- Utilization factor = User Housing units / 3
- Difficulty factor factor

Difficulty level:

High – 1.5

Moderate – 1.25

Low -1

- Socio Economic exception (Table 4.10)

Technical estimation was done after the fund allocation and allocated fix amount of money for each road without considering completeness of the project and focusing of number of projects rather than completed projects. Even though professionals feel that a fair amount of money allocated for the projects they strongly emphasize that politicians had the potential to significantly impact on money allocation and that it was apolitical trick to appease the people carrying out large number of projects with small project value.

Follow up study suggest that majority of the projects are incomplete and there are reasonable number of projects where deficiency amount is equals or less than fifty thousand rupees.

Professionals clearly emphasized that type of road selection decision was dominant by professionals and majority of professionals' state that political and civilians had a moderate decision-making influence on the road type.

According to the Field survey construction methods summary 82% of the rural roads were concrete roads ILB and macadam roads are around 08-09 % and earth roads are only 1.8% from total sample roads.

Though majority of the roads were constructed in concrete construction professionals prefer ILB and earth roads ahead of concrete roads.

In conclusion there are few projects which can contribute towards socio-economic development and majority of the projects are disadvantageous because of bad strategies followed by the government and allowing political interference to dominate the projects rather than allowing technical experts to execute a beneficial product.

CHAPTER 6

6.1 Recommendation

To obtain efficient and effective socio-economic benefits from rural roads some important recommendations can be mentioned as follows.

Analysis emphasized that majority of the projects are disadvantageous. To overcome that in a future RDP stakeholder should collaboratively contribute to execute a successful project

Professionals emphasized that pre-construction stage activities are dominated by political interference which should be controlled by the government and allow technically qualified professionals to select projects through a proper feasibility study.

Through a sample field survey and a post feasibility study generalized formula was formed define boundaries with expert judgement which can be used as a selection criterion to achieve a feasible project.

Generalized formula

Final score = (Utilization factor *Difficulty factor) + Socio Economic exception

- Utilization factor = User Housing units / 3
- Difficulty factor factor

Difficulty level:

High – 1.5

Moderate – 1.25

Low -1

- Socio Economic exception (Table 4.10)

It was found that majority of the projects are incomplete and there are reasonable number of projects where deficiency amount is equals or less than fifty thousand rupees. Also estimate the project after allocating a fix amount of money for the particular project which is a bad practice. So, it is recommended to allocate funds after doing a proper feasibility study and a technical estimation by a technically qualified professional.

Selection of type of construction method decision was dominated by technically qualified professionals which is a good prospect. Moderate influence from politicians also should me minimized because considering the subgrade condition, drainage, traffic considerations and durability technical qualified professional should recommend the road type.

Finally, it is recommended to strengthen government strategies of rural road development and impose proper engineering techniques for the pre-construction stage of rural road development.

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8. ANNEXTURE

8.1 Sample roads

8.2 Questionnaire

8.3 Sample Survey Report

8.4 Sample road type, cost and coverage area

8.5 Expert judgement

8.6 Sample Roads Mobility

8.7 Post feasibility analysis

8.8 Completion

Annexure 01

Sample Roads

Selected sampling Technique - Simple Random Sampling

S/N	Project Ref.No.	GN Division	Project	Project Amount
Panadura - Divisional secretariat				
1	P 4	Keselwatta	Development of Suhada Lane	500,000.00
2	P 46	Pattiya North	Paving Interlocking blocks to remaining part of second lane of Madakubura	500,000.00
3	P 56	Pattiya South	Development of Medananda road, by road towards Mr. Gunaruwan's House	500,000.00
4	P 88	kuda Wadduwa	Development of Lankarama road first lane towards south	500,000.00
Bandaragama - Divisional secretariat				
5	B 1	Raigama South	Concreting of 02nd lane of Raigamthuduwa (Road leading towards Mr. Amarasiri's House and other houses)	500,000.00
6	B 29	Bamunumulla (Muslim)	Concreting of road near Mr. Rashid's House	500,000.00
7	B 54	Bandaragama East	Development of Kalutara road by road near Mrs. Chithra Perera's House.	500,000.00
8	B 71	Bolgoda	Development of by road of Bolgoda, Leading towards Mr. Anura's house and other houses	300,000.00
Horana - Divisional secretariat				
9	H 12	Olaboduwa East	Development of ibula road by DBST method (With drainage system)	1,500,000.00
10	H 15	Welmilla	Concreting of Mathri mawatha 02nd by road steep part (Up from near paddy field)	500,000.00
11	H 30	Kulapana	Concreting of 03rd by road of Chandika Preethi Tiraj mawatha	500,000.00
12	H 100	Lower Millawa south	Development of Koshena main road	500,000.00
Ingiriya - Divisional secretariat				
13	I 32	Aduragala	Development of the remaining part of the main road in the upper part of Aduragala estate	500,000.00
14	I 54	Batugampala	Development of the road to Gonabadiwala	500,000.00
15	I 68	Kurana south	Development of the road leading to the hill top water tank near Kurana Primary School	500,000.00
16	I 72	Kurana North	Concreting of Dullahara 02nd lane	500,000.00
Bulathsinhala - Divisional secretariat				
17	BU 4	Lower Naragala	Concreting of road in front of Mrs. U.D. Sumanawathi's house	500,000.00
18	BU 37	Polegoda west	Concreting of the road that goes near Kuruduwatta Samaranayake Pre-School	500,000.00
19	BU 100	Lower Welgama	Developing the road towards Mr. premarathna's house of lower welgama	500,000.00
20	BU 123	Molkawa	Developing the sewa piyasa road	500,000.00

S/N	Project Ref.No.	GN Division	Project	Project Amount
Madurawala - Divisional secretariat				
21	M 1	Kadana north	Developing the road in front of Mr. Gunasinghe's house	500,000.00
22	M 17	Walpita	Developing the road from near Mr. Saman kumara's house to Mr. Aruna Nishantha's house	500,000.00
23	M 34	Lower Karannagoda	Setting up an agricultural road to travel to Ranhingoda Hunukatiya paddy field	500,000.00
24	M 48	Warakagoda north	Developing the Godapara heena Magurugaladeniya road	500,000.00
Millaniya - Divisional secretariat				
25	MI 4	Uduwara North	Developing the road in front of boralukatiyawatta garment factory	500,000.00
26	MI 15	Pathakada	Developing the Alagoda main road	500,000.00
27	MI 54	Millaniya	Developing the road towards Mr.Iresh's house and other houses of Boddalgoda	500,000.00
28	MI 105	Pethigamuwa south	Developing the Mohottiwatta road	500,000.00
Kalutara - Divisional secretariat				
29	K 19	Moronthuduwa north	Development of road from near Mr.Nalinda's house by ILB paving	500,000.00
30	K 72	Ethanamadala	development of road from near buddah statue of Walakadawatta	900,000.00
31	K 91	Kuruduwatta	Development of Byroad of Thusitarama Road	500,000.00
32	K 118	Kalamulla south	Development of the road to the house of Mr.Pradeep Kumara from galle road.	500,000.00
Beruwala - Divisional secretariat				
33	BE 12	Kuda payagala north	Developing the road which carrying the sorole on Saint Mary's Mawatha	1,000,000.00
34	BE 59	Marakkalawatta	Development of the road in front of Mr. Ithak's shop, Marakkalawatta First Lane	500,000.00
35	BE 69	Badanagoda	Development of the by road starting near the house of Mr. S.A. Thivanka of Manhandiya	500,000.00
36	BE 86	Welipitiya	Development of road from 145/26 SM Road near Mrs. Fatima Aleviya's house to Mr. Mohammad Munauwar's house	500,000.00
Dodangoda - Divisional secretariat				
37	D 2	Adikarigoda	Development of the road from Mr. Karunaratne's house to Mr. M.K Ajith's house	500,000.00
38	D 14	Remunagoda north	Dvelopment of byroad (road towarda Mr. Michael's house)of the schon thuna road.	500,000.00
39	D 77	Nabada west	Development of main road towards cloden states.	500,000.00
40	D 102	Palpitiyagoda	Development of Kabaravila Haritapura main road slopes	500,000.00

S/N	Project Ref.No.	GN Division	Project	Project Amount
Matugama - Divisional secretariat				
41	MA 2	Bondupitiya	Development of the by road of henegangoda bodiya road	500,000.00
42	MA 29	Ladduwa	Development of road way to Dewagoda school	500,000.00
43	MA 58	Nawththuduwa	Development of byroad of ranaviru Nimal mawatha	500,000.00
44	MA 90	Henegama	development of road near Mr.Dinesh's house of Rameeya thabilikotuwa	500,000.00
Agalawatta - Divisional secretariat				
45	A 17	Kakulandala north	Development of the road starting near Mr. Galmuddarawatta Dhanoj's house	500,000.00
46	A 36	Bodiyakanda	Development of the road ahead from near the house of Nelumkatihena Mr. J.D. Samarasinghe.	500,000.00
47	A 55	Kevitiyagala	Development of byroad near the Delgahayata shop of Kevitiyagala Gamagewatta	500,000.00
48	A 60	Kalupahana	Development of the entrance road to themaha kalupahana temple	500,000.00
Palindanuwara - Divisional secretariat				
49	PA 7	Lathpadura	Development of Ambalanovita dolkit road by DBST method	500,000.00
50	PA 29	Kapugedara	Development of Kapugedara school road	1,000,000.00
51	PA 56	Bampara	Development of first byroad(Road near Mr.Tikiribandara's house) of Kallewatta to kuburuhena road	1,000,000.00
52	PA 84	Magura West	Development of first lane of kajugaswila road near Mr. Sirisena's house	500,000.00
Walalavita - Divisional secretariat				
53	W 2	Ittapana South	Concreting of byroad near temple	500,000.00
54	W 14	Ittapana North	Concreting of Gallanthuduwa road	500,000.00
55	W 99	Kankotawatta	Development of fruit business No.01 road	500,000.00
56	W 117	Bothalawa	Development of kahatagalla road (From near community hall)	500,000.00

Evaluation on Pre Construction Stage of Rural Roads Constructed Under "Sapirigamak" Rural Development Programme - 2020, Kalutara District, Sri Lanka.

Dear Sir / Madam,

First, I would like to thank you for your time. I am L. G. S. De Silva, an Undergraduate of University of Vocational Technology, Ratmalana, Sri Lanka. Conducting Research as partial fulfillment of the requirement of B.Tech. in Construction Technology and Resource Management Degree. My study is about an evaluation on pre construction stage of Rural Roads Constructed Under "Sapirigamak" Rural Development Programme - 2020, Kalutara District, Sri Lanka. Please read all the statements given below carefully and give your true opinion, as it is vital for the success of this study.

Note - Please fill the questionnaire if you have experience "Sapirigamak" Rural Development Programme.

Thank you.

For any query contact through gayansilvalive@gmail.com

* Required

Personal Details

All the below details are fully private and confidential.

1. Designation / Status *

Mark only one oval.

- Engineer
- Deputy/Assistant Director Planning
- Technical Officer

**Overall
Impression on
the
"sapirigamak" RDP**

Please convey your first impression to the mind comparing the "sapirigamak" rural development programme with your previous experience on rural road development programmes and current situation of the country.

Project value - Approx.1.5 billion (Kalutara District)
RDP - Rural Development Programme.

2. "Sapiri gamak" RDP 2020, Compared to previous RDP.

Mark only one oval.

- Positively changed
- Negatively changed
- No significant changes
- Other: _____

3. Do you think that the "sapirigamak" RDP was well planned to contribute to the economic development of the country?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

4. Do you think that the "sapirigamak" RDP was well planned to contribute to the social development of the country?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

7. What is your preferred road selection influence level? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Nil	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
Technically qualified professionals.	<input type="radio"/>					
Admin. service/Planning service officers.	<input type="radio"/>					
Field officers	<input type="radio"/>					
Ministry Level	<input type="radio"/>					
Politicians	<input type="radio"/>					
Civilians	<input type="radio"/>					

8. What aspect should be given top priority when selecting a rural road?

Mark only one oval.

- Contribution to the economic development
- Contribution to the Social development
- Both

9. Essential roads to be developed were considered as priority while selecting roads.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

Pre Construction Stage - Fund Allocation/Estimation

10. Please rate following statements as your satisfaction level in the below scale of 1 is Strongly Disagree to 5 is Strongly Agree.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
"Technical estimation was done after the fund allocation". Do you agree with this strategy of "Sapirigamak" RDP	<input type="radio"/>				
"A fix amount allocated for each project without consideration of completeness". Do you agree with this strategy of "Sapirigamak" RDP	<input type="radio"/>				
"Focused on number of projects rather than complete projects". Do you agree with this strategy of "Sapirigamak" RDP	<input type="radio"/>				
A good allocation amount was received for the RDP	<input type="radio"/>				
Professionals had the potential to significantly impact on fund allocation	<input type="radio"/>				
Politicians had the potential to significantly impact on fund allocation	<input type="radio"/>				
It was a political trick to appease the people, carrying out a large number of	<input type="radio"/>				

projects with small project value

11. What is your order of choice in road construction methods in kalutara district?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Concrete Roads	DBST Roads	Interlocking Paving Block Roads	Earth Roads (Cut/Fill)
1st Choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2nd Choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3rd Choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4th Choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. What is the reason for the answer for previous question as per your opinion?

Mark only one oval per row.

	01st Reason	02nd Reason	03rd Reason
Length	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Comfortability to transportation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Durability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Aesthetic appearance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cost	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Easiness of execution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Environmental friendliness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Proper drainage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. The method of construction of the road is decided while preparing the estimate can be depend on following factors. **Rate the influence of the factors.**

Mark only one oval per row.

	Nil	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
Professional recommendation	<input type="radio"/>					
Political preference	<input type="radio"/>					
Civilian preference	<input type="radio"/>					

Thank you very much for your time and effort.

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Google Forms

Survey Report
RURAL ROADS UNDER SAPIRIGAMAK PROGRAMME 2020 - KALUTARA DISTRICT

Divisional Secretariat - Date -

Project -

Ref. No -

SECONDARY DATA

01. Constructed method - Concrete ILB Macada m Earth

02. Length of road (Completed under the project) -m

03. Average width of road -m 04. Average thickness of road -m

05. Cost of construction - Rs.....

06. Miscellaneous data -

PRIMARY DATA

07. Approx. length of remaining undeveloped road area -m

08. Mobility (Depending on user comments)

Road mobility before construction -

very bad Bad Not bad Good Very good

Road mobility after construction -

very bad Bad Not bad Good Very good

09. Accessibility (Depending on inspection and considering user comments)

Social Aspect	No. of units/extent	Economic Aspect	No. of units/extent
Housing units		Export agricultural land	
Feeding local \ collector roads		Consumption agricultural land	
Collecting private / rural roads		A tourist attraction	
Schools		Tourist hotel	
Post office/Police station/Samurdhi bank		Factories	
GN/DO/SDO/ARPA office		industries	
Clinics		self-employed industries	
Religious places/cemetery		Horticulture	
play grounds and parks			

***Omit developments in past 02 years (After rural road development)**

10. Other Comments -

.....

Annexure 04

Sample road type, cost and coverage area

S/N	Pro. Ref.No.	Construction Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Road Width(m)	Road Length(m)	Surface Area of road(Sq.m)
1	P 4	Concrete	500,000.00	3	56.5	169.5
2	P 56	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
3	P 88	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	45	164.25
4	B 1	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67
5	B 29	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455
6	B 71	Concrete	300,000.00	2.1	49	102.9
7	H 15	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57	171
8	H 30	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
9	H 100	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	47	171.55
10	I 32	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5
11	I 54	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57	171
12	I 68	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	62	169.88
13	I 72	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70.5	171.315
14	BU 4	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	71	172.53
15	BU 37	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61	167.14
16	BU 100	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
17	BU 123	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	60.5	165.77
18	M 1	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885
19	M 17	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5
20	MI 4	Concrete	500,000.00	4.5	38	171
21	MI 15	Concrete	500,000.00	3.96	43	170.28
22	MI 54	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885
23	K 72	Concrete	550,000.00	3.65	51	186.15
24	K 91	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
25	K 118	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67
26	BE 12	Concrete	625,000.00	3.65	58	211.7
27	BE 59	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61	167.14
28	BE 69	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61.5	168.51
29	D 2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
30	D 14	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174
31	D 102	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66
32	MA 2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885
33	MA 29	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	58.5	213.525
34	MA 58	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1
35	MA 90	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66
36	A 17	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67
37	A 36	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174
38	A 55	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455
39	A 60	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	59	215.35
40	PA 29	Concrete	1,000,000.00	3.96	87	344.52
41	PA 56	Concrete	1,000,000.00	2.43	140	340.2
42	PA 84	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67
43	W 2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455
44	W 14	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174
45	W 99	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5
46	W 117	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66
			23,975,000.00			8,206.99

S/N	Pro. Ref.No.	Construction Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Road Width(m)	Road Length(m)	Surface Area of road(Sq.m)
1	P 46	ILB	500,000.00	2.43	46	111.78
2	B 54	ILB	500,000.00	3	37	111
3	K 19	ILB	500,000.00	2.43	45	109.35
4	BE 86	ILB	500,000.00	3	37.5	112.5
<u>2,000,000.00</u>						<u>444.63</u>
1	H 12	Macadam	800,000.00	3.65	113	412.45
2	M 48	Macadam	500,000.00	3	90	270
3	MI 105	Macadam	500,000.00	2.74	95	260.3
4	D 77	Macadam	500,000.00	3	85	255
5	PA 7	Macadam	500,000.00	3	88	264
<u>2,800,000.00</u>						<u>1,461.75</u>
1	M 34	Earth	500,000.00	3.35	102	341.7
<u>500,000.00</u>						<u>341.70</u>

Annexure 05

Expert Review (Discussion Summary)

Date: 22-09-2022

Location: District secretariat Kalutara – Engineering Division

Participants:

Eng. D.C.N. Kalansooriya (Former District engineer - Kalutara)

Eng. R.S.P. Ranasinghe (District Engineer - Kalutara)

L.G.S. De Silva (Student)

Discussion on Road construction method - summary

ILB roads have good drainage properties where concrete is an impervious surface. And also, durable, in addition to the base additional quarry dust or sand layer is there in the ILB roads and the compressive strength of a paving block is about 25N/mm², where concrete construction was done with 20N/mm² concrete mix. Aesthetic appearance is better. As a limited budget is approving for each rural road earth roads and macadam roads are a good option. But with the moderate influence of politicians in road type selection sometimes professionals have to select the road type satisfying the users as well as the politician of the respective village. Sometimes though the ILB is advantageous in terms of durability and strength is is better to execute the project in concrete or macadam considering the completeness of the project.

Macadam roads are less in strength and durability compared to concrete roads and it is not suitable for areas which have inundation problems and drainage issues which can be subject to fast deterioration.

Discussion on rural road selection criteria - summary

In the post feasibility study, all the dimensions are available and it is necessary to generalize the equation.

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \frac{\text{User Housing units}}{\text{Coverage area(m}^2\text{)}} * \text{Length of road(m)}$$

Generalization,

Descriptive statics data,

<i>Coverage Area</i>		<i>Length of road(m)</i>	
Mean	186.6977	Mean	65.46
Median	170.1	Median	61.25
Mode	170.1	Mode	70.00
Range	309.55	Range	103.00
Minimum	102.9	Minimum	37.00
Maximum	412.45	Maximum	140.00
Sum	10455.07	Sum	3665.50
Count	56	Count	56.00

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} * \frac{\text{Length of road(m)}}{\text{Coverage area(m}^2\text{)}}$$

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} * \frac{65.46\text{m}}{196.7\text{m}^2}$$

$$\text{Utilization factor (F)} = \text{User Housing units} / 3$$

As per the expert judgement low difficulty level (good mobility) rural road should be develop if the user housing units equals or more than 30 to gain socio economic benefits as the minimum requirement.

Boundary score for feasibility check = $30/3 = 10$

So feasible project score ≥ 10

Difficulty factor factor (H)

Difficulty level

High – 1.5

Moderate – 1.25

Low -1

Difficulty level varies from 1-1.5 according to the difficulty level observed in the feasibility checking stage reasonable value can be use.

Economic/Social Development exceptions

Following exceptional socio-economic aspects were rated and imposed a score by expert judgment.

Class	Exceptions	Score
<u>Economic Exceptions</u>		
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export agricultural land • Consumption agricultural land • Factories • industries 	10
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A tourist attraction • Tourist hotel 	7
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-employed industries • Horticulture 	5

<u>Social Exceptions</u>		
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools 	7
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post office/Police station/Samurdhi bank • GN/DO/SDO/ARPA office • Clinics 	5
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious places/cemetery • play grounds and parks 	3

Final feasibility check for rural roads

Generalized formula

Final score = (Utilization factor *Difficulty factor) + Socio Economic exception

Annexure 06

Sample Roads Mobility

Likert scale

- 1 → Very Good
 2 → Good
 3 → Not Bad
 4 → Bad
 5 → Very Bad

S/ N	Project Ref.No.	Method	Mobility before				Mobility after				Mobility improvement (A-B)	Mobility improvement
			User Review		Score (A)	User Review		Score (B)				
1	P 4	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	1	1.67	1.67	Improved
2	P 46	ILB	3	2	3	2.67	2	1	2	1.67	1.00	Improved
3	P 56	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	1	1.67	1.33	Improved
4	P 88	Concrete	4	3	3	3.33	1	1	2	1.33	2.00	Improved
5	B 1	Concrete	3	3	2	2.67	2	1	2	1.67	1.00	Improved
6	B 29	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	1	2	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
7	B 54	ILB	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
8	B 71	Concrete	3	3	4	3.33	1	2	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
9	H 12	Macadam	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
10	H 15	Concrete	5	4	5	4.67	1	1	1	1.00	3.67	Improved
11	H 30	Concrete	3	2	3	2.67	2	2	2	2.00	0.67	Improved
12	H 100	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	1	1	1.33	2.00	Improved
13	I 32	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
14	I 54	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
15	I 68	Concrete	3	3	4	3.33	2	1	1	1.33	2.00	Improved
16	I 72	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	1	2	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
17	BU 4	Concrete	4	3	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
18	BU 37	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
19	BU 100	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	1	1.67	1.67	Improved
20	BU 123	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
21	M 1	Concrete	3	3	4	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
22	M 17	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
23	M 34	Earth	4	3	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
24	M 48	Macadam	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
25	MI 4	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
26	MI 15	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
27	MI 54	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	1	2	1	1.33	1.67	Improved
28	MI 105	Macadam	3	3	4	3.33	2	1	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
29	K 19	ILB	3	4	3	3.33	2	1	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
30	K 72	Concrete	2	3	3	2.67	2	2	2	2.00	0.67	Improved
31	K 91	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	1	2	1	1.33	2.00	Improved
32	K 118	Concrete	3	3	2	2.67	2	2	2	2.00	0.67	Improved
33	BE 12	Concrete	2	3	3	2.67	2	2	2	2.00	0.67	Improved

S/ N	Project Ref.No.	Method	Mobility before				Mobility after				Mobility improvement (A-B)	Mobility improvement
			User Review			Score (A)	User Review			Score (B)		
34	BE 59	Concrete	3	2	3	2.67	2	2	2	2.00	0.67	Improved
35	BE 69	Concrete	3	2	3	2.67	2	1	1	1.33	1.33	Improved
36	BE 86	ILB	3	4	3	3.33	1	2	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
37	D 2	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
38	D 14	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
39	D 77	Macadam	4	3	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
40	D 102	Concrete	4	5	5	4.67	2	1	1	1.33	3.33	Improved
41	MA 2	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2.00	1.00	Improved
42	MA 29	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
43	MA 58	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
44	MA 90	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
45	A 17	Concrete	3	3	4	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
46	A 36	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	1	1.67	1.33	Improved
47	A 55	Concrete	4	3	3	3.33	2	1	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
48	A 60	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	1	2	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
49	PA 7	Macadam	3	3	4	3.33	2	1	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
50	PA 29	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
51	PA 56	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
52	PA 84	Concrete	4	3	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
53	W 2	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved
54	W 14	Concrete	3	3	4	3.33	1	2	2	1.67	1.67	Improved
55	W 99	Concrete	3	4	3	3.33	2	2	2	2.00	1.33	Improved
56	W 117	Concrete	3	3	3	3.00	2	1	2	1.67	1.33	Improved

mobility before (SoreA) - stastical analisis

Mean	3.15
Median	3.00
Mode	3.33
Standard Deviation	0.38
Range	2.00
Minimum	2.67
Maximum	4.67
Sum	176.67
Count	56.00
Largest(10)	3.33
Smallest(10)	3.00

Annexure 07

Post feasibility study - Metrix chart

S/ N	Project Ref.No.	Constructed Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Width of road(m) A	Length (m) B	Area(Sq. m) C = A*B	User s(No s.) D	Users /Sq.m E=D/C	Utilizat ion factorF =E*B	Road difficulty level (User reviews) G	Difficult y factor H=G*1.5/ 4.6	Utilizatio n difficulty index I=F*H	Economic/Social Development exceptions		Final Score I+J
													Score J	Remarks	
1	P4	Concrete	500,000.00	3	56.5	169.5	5	0.03	1.67	3.33	1.07	1.79			1.79
2	P46	ILB	500,000.00	2.43	46	111.78	10	0.09	4.12	2.67	0.86	3.53			3.53
3	P56	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	10	0.06	4.12	3.00	0.96	3.97			3.97
4	P88	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	45	164.25	11	0.07	3.01	3.33	1.07	3.23			3.23
5	B1	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67	5	0.03	2.06	2.67	0.86	1.76			1.76
6	B29	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455	13	0.08	5.35	3.00	0.96	5.16			5.16
7	B54	ILB	500,000.00	3	37	111	11	0.10	3.67	3.00	0.96	3.54			3.54
8	B71	Concrete	300,000.00	2.1	49	102.9	5	0.05	2.38	3.33	1.07	2.55			2.55
9	H12	Macadam	800,000.00	3.65	113	412.45	85	0.21	23.29	3.00	0.96	22.46			22.46
10	H15	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57	171	12	0.07	4.00	4.67	1.50	6.00	10	Paddy field	16.00
11	H30	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	8	0.05	3.29	2.67	0.86	2.82			2.82
12	H100	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	47	171.55	15	0.09	4.11	3.33	1.07	4.40			4.40
13	I32	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5	12	0.07	4.00	3.00	0.96	3.86	20	tea factory and Plantation	23.86
14	I54	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57	171	16	0.09	5.33	3.00	0.96	5.14			5.14
15	I68	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	62	169.88	18	0.11	6.57	3.33	1.07	7.04	7	School	14.04
16	I72	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70.5	171.315	8	0.05	3.29	3.00	0.96	3.17			3.17
17	BU4	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	71	172.53	6	0.03	2.47	3.33	1.07	2.65			2.65
18	BU37	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61	167.14	25	0.15	9.12	3.00	0.96	8.80	6	Pre-Scholl, Play ground	14.80
19	BU100	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	9	0.05	3.70	3.33	1.07	3.97			3.97
20	BU123	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	60.5	165.77	30	0.18	10.95	3.00	0.96	10.56	5	GN/DO/SDO/ARPA office	15.56
21	M1	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885	11	0.07	4.53	3.33	1.07	4.85			4.85
22	M17	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5	6	0.03	2.00	3.00	0.96	1.93			1.93
23	M34	Earth	500,000.00	3.35	102	341.7	4	0.01	1.19	3.33	1.07	1.28	10	Paddy field	11.28
24	M48	Macadam	500,000.00	3	90	270	15	0.06	5.00	3.33	1.07	5.36			5.36
25	MI4	Concrete	500,000.00	4.5	38	171	20	0.12	4.44	3.33	1.07	4.76	10	Garment	14.76
26	MI15	Concrete	500,000.00	3.96	43	170.28	18	0.11	4.55	3.00	0.96	4.38			4.38
27	MI54	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885	5	0.03	2.06	3.00	0.96	1.98			1.98
28	MI105	Macadam	500,000.00	2.74	95	260.3	35	0.13	12.77	3.33	1.07	13.69			13.69

S/N	Project Ref.No.		Constructed Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Width of road(m) A	Length (m) B	Area(Sq.m) C = A*B	Users(No.s.) D	Users /Sq.m E=D/C	Utilization factor F =E*B	Road difficulty level (User reviews) G	Difficulty factor H=G*1.5/4.6	Utilization difficulty index I=F*H	Economic/Social Development exceptions		Final Score I+J
														Score J	Remarks	
29	K	19	ILB	500,000.00	2.43	45	109.35	8	0.07	3.29	3.33	1.07	3.53			3.53
30	K	72	Concrete	550,000.00	3.65	51	186.15	12	0.06	3.29	2.67	0.86	2.82			2.82
31	K	91	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	7	0.04	2.88	3.33	1.07	3.09			3.09
32	K	118	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67	13	0.08	5.35	2.67	0.86	4.59			4.59
33	BE	12	Concrete	625,000.00	3.65	58	211.7	25	0.12	6.85	2.67	0.86	5.87			5.87
34	BE	59	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61	167.14	20	0.12	7.30	2.67	0.86	6.26			6.26
35	BE	69	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	61.5	168.51	8	0.05	2.92	2.67	0.86	2.50			2.50
36	BE	86	ILB	500,000.00	3	37.5	112.5	5	0.04	1.67	3.33	1.07	1.79			1.79
37	D	2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	9	0.05	3.70	3.00	0.96	3.57			3.57
38	D	14	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174	11	0.06	3.67	3.00	0.96	3.54			3.54
39	D	77	Macadam	500,000.00	3	85	255	65	0.25	21.67	3.33	1.07	23.21			23.21
40	D	102	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66	45	0.28	16.42	4.67	1.50	24.64			24.64
41	MA	2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69.5	168.885	8	0.05	3.29	3.00	0.96	3.17			3.17
42	MA	29	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	58.5	213.525	25	0.12	6.85	3.00	0.96	6.60	7	School	13.60
43	MA	58	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	70	170.1	7	0.04	2.88	3.33	1.07	3.09			3.09
44	MA	90	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66	6	0.04	2.19	3.00	0.96	2.11			2.11
45	A	17	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67	14	0.08	5.76	3.33	1.07	6.17			6.17
46	A	36	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174	8	0.05	2.67	3.00	0.96	2.57			2.57
47	A	55	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455	10	0.06	4.12	3.33	1.07	4.41			4.41
48	A	60	Concrete	500,000.00	3.65	59	215.35	3	0.01	0.82	3.00	0.96	0.79	3	Temple	3.79
49	PA	7	Macadam	500,000.00	3	88	264	50	0.19	16.67	3.33	1.07	17.86			17.86
50	PA	29	Concrete	1,000,000.00	3.96	87	344.52	30	0.09	7.58	3.33	1.07	8.12	7	School	15.12
51	PA	56	Concrete	1,000,000.00	2.43	140	340.2	10	0.03	4.12	3.00	0.96	3.97			3.97
52	PA	84	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	69	167.67	5	0.03	2.06	3.33	1.07	2.20			2.20
53	W	2	Concrete	500,000.00	2.43	68.5	166.455	7	0.04	2.88	3.00	0.96	2.78			2.78
54	W	14	Concrete	500,000.00	3	58	174	20	0.11	6.67	3.33	1.07	7.14			7.14
55	W	99	Concrete	500,000.00	3	57.5	172.5	18	0.10	6.00	3.33	1.07	6.43	5	Self employed industry	11.43
56	W	117	Concrete	500,000.00	2.74	59	161.66	12	0.07	4.38	3.00	0.96	4.22			4.22

<i>Final Score</i>	
Mean	7.17
Median	4.10
Mode	3.53
Standard Deviation	6.42
Sample Variance	41.15
Kurtosis	0.94
Range	22.87
Minimum	1.76
Maximum	24.64
Sum	401.65
Count	56.00
Largest(10)	14.76
Smallest(10)	2.57

Expert Review Decision -

Boundary Definition

- Final score ≥ 10 Feasible Project
- Final score < 10 Non Feasible Project

(* See expert review annexure for more details)

Annexure 08

Completion

S/N	Project Ref.No.	Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Length (m)	remaining undeveloped length(m)	undeveloped length(%)	Developed length %	Fund deficiency(Rs.)
1	P 4	Concrete	500,000.00	56.5	8	12	88	62,015.50
2	P 46	ILB	500,000.00	46	0	0	100	Completed
3	P 56	Concrete	500,000.00	70	10	13	88	62,500.00
4	P 88	Concrete	500,000.00	45	5	10	90	50,000.00
5	B 1	Concrete	500,000.00	69	0	0	100	Completed
6	B 29	Concrete	500,000.00	68.5	8	10	90	52,287.58
7	B 54	ILB	500,000.00	37	12	24	76	122,448.98
8	B 71	Concrete	300,000.00	49	5	9	91	27,777.78
9	H 12	Macadam	800,000.00	113	60	35	65	277,456.65
10	H 15	Concrete	500,000.00	57	12	17	83	86,956.52
11	H 30	Concrete	500,000.00	70	0	0	100	Completed
12	H 100	Concrete	500,000.00	47	30	39	61	194,805.19
13	I 32	Concrete	500,000.00	57.5	35	38	62	189,189.19
14	I 54	Concrete	500,000.00	57	40	41	59	206,185.57
15	I 68	Concrete	500,000.00	62	20	24	76	121,951.22
16	I 72	Concrete	500,000.00	70.5	8	10	90	50,955.41
17	BU 4	Concrete	500,000.00	71	0	0	100	Completed
18	BU 37	Concrete	500,000.00	61	25	29	71	145,348.84
19	BU 100	Concrete	500,000.00	70	0	0	100	Completed
20	BU 123	Concrete	500,000.00	60.5	18	23	77	114,649.68
21	M 1	Concrete	500,000.00	69.5	7	9	91	45,751.63
22	M 17	Concrete	500,000.00	57.5	0	0	100	Completed
23	M 34	Earth	500,000.00	102	0	0	100	Completed
24	M 48	Macadam	500,000.00	90	25	22	78	108,695.65
25	MI 4	Concrete	500,000.00	38	10	21	79	104,166.67
26	MI 15	Concrete	500,000.00	43	18	30	70	147,540.98
27	MI 54	Concrete	500,000.00	69.5	0	0	100	Completed
28	MI 105	Macadam	500,000.00	95	12	11	89	56,074.77
29	K 19	ILB	500,000.00	45	6	12	88	58,823.53
30	K 72	Concrete	550,000.00	51	0	0	100	Completed
31	K 91	Concrete	500,000.00	70	0	0	100	Completed
32	K 118	Concrete	500,000.00	69	6	8	92	40,000.00
33	BE 12	Concrete	625,000.00	58	0	0	100	Completed
34	BE 59	Concrete	500,000.00	61	9	13	87	64,285.71
35	BE 69	Concrete	500,000.00	61.5	0	0	100	Completed
36	BE 86	ILB	500,000.00	37.5	0	0	100	Completed
37	D 2	Concrete	500,000.00	70	8	10	90	51,282.05
38	D 14	Concrete	500,000.00	58	10	15	85	73,529.41
39	D 77	Macadam	500,000.00	85	40	32	68	160,000.00
40	D 102	Concrete	500,000.00	59	25	30	70	148,809.52
41	MA 2	Concrete	500,000.00	69.5	5	7	93	33,557.05
42	MA 29	Concrete	500,000.00	58.5	15	20	80	102,040.82
43	MA 58	Concrete	500,000.00	70	0	0	100	Completed
44	MA 90	Concrete	500,000.00	59	0	0	100	Completed

S/N	Project Ref.No.	Method	Project Amount(Rs.)	Length (m)	remaining undeveloped length(m)	undeveloped length(%)	Developed length %	Fund deficiency(Rs.)
45	A 17	Concrete	500,000.00	69	7	9	91	46,052.63
46	A 36	Concrete	500,000.00	58	8	12	88	60,606.06
47	A 55	Concrete	500,000.00	68.5	7	9	91	46,357.62
48	A 60	Concrete	500,000.00	59	0	0	100	Completed
49	PA 7	Macadam	500,000.00	88	35	28	72	142,276.42
50	PA 29	Concrete	1,000,000.00	87	25	22	78	223,214.29
51	PA 56	Concrete	1,000,000.00	140	5	3	97	34,482.76
52	PA 84	Concrete	500,000.00	69	3	4	96	20,833.33
53	W 2	Concrete	500,000.00	68.5	7	9	91	46,357.62
54	W 14	Concrete	500,000.00	58	35	38	62	188,172.04
55	W 99	Concrete	500,000.00	57.5	10	15	85	74,074.07
56	W 117	Concrete	500,000.00	59	15	20	80	101,351.35

Completed rural roads

Fund deficiency ≤ Rs. 50,000